

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL NETWORKS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The article examines the influence of social networks on the development of the modern Russian language. It analyzes the main linguistic phenomena emerging in the context of digital communication: abbreviations and acronyms, borrowing and adaptation of foreign words, the spread of internet slang and memes, and the transformation of written language norms. Special attention is given to the positive and negative aspects of the influence of social networks on the language: their role in the democratization and creative development of the language, as well as the risks associated with simplification and violation of grammatical norms. The conclusion highlights the need for a conscious approach to language culture in the digital age to preserve the richness and uniqueness of the Russian language.

Keywords: social networks, Russian language, internet slang, borrowings, abbreviations, memes, communication language, digital communication, language transformation.

Social networks have become an integral part of modern life, significantly influencing various aspects of human communication and behavior. User interactions in social networks not only create a new culture of communication but also actively affect the language, including the Russian language. This article explores how social networks contribute to the development and change of the modern Russian language, what linguistic phenomena they generate, and what positive and negative aspects they bring to the language. Social networks create a unique communication environment characterized by high dynamism and the need for quick information exchange. This leads to the emergence of brief and simplified forms of expression. In social network communication, people tend to be concise, which often manifests in the use of abbreviations and acronyms. For example, instead of full spellings of words and expressions, users employ forms like "PM" (private message), "pls" (please), and "IMHO" (in my humble opinion). These abbreviations become part of everyday written speech, influencing oral communication and gradually permeating spoken language.

One of the most significant phenomena in the development of the Russian language under the influence of social networks is the active borrowing of foreign words, primarily Anglicisms. Words like "follower," "like," "post," and "story" have firmly entered the everyday communication of social network users. This process occurs due to globalization and the close connection with English-speaking culture, which dominates the internet. Borrowed words are often adapted and modified in the Russian language, acquiring new forms and meanings. For example, the word "like" initially meant "to like," but now it can also denote an action — "to like" (to give a like). Such lexical innovations expand the expressive possibilities of the Russian

language but simultaneously raise concerns among linguists, as excessive borrowing can blur boundaries and lead to the loss of language uniqueness.

An important aspect related to the influence of social networks is the creation and spread of internet memes and slang. Memes represent a special form of cultural phenomenon, where text and visual images combine to convey a specific meaning. These short expressions and phrases often have a humorous character and quickly spread across the network, becoming popular among the youth. As a result, new words and expressions emerge, becoming part of everyday speech. For instance, phrases like "crush" (object of affection), "top" (best), or "to get in" (to get into trouble) are actively used by young people both online and in real life. Slang born in the internet environment serves an important function — it allows individuals to express their belonging to a particular social group and demonstrate their involvement in modern culture. However, the use of such language may lead to a simplification of vocabulary and a violation of grammatical norms. The role of social networks in the transformation of written language should be noted separately. Communication in social networks often does not require strict adherence to grammatical and punctuation rules, leading to changes in the norms of written language. Users frequently neglect punctuation, use shortened and simplified forms of words, and disregard text formatting norms. This attitude towards language gradually becomes normalized, and users begin to perceive it as natural. As a result, the youth, actively interacting in social networks, may lose the skill of proper writing and sentence construction, negatively affecting the overall level of literacy. On the other hand, social networks also give rise to a new direction — creative writing, where people play with language, creating original expressions, unusual text forms, and visual effects, contributing to the development of creative thinking and linguistic creativity.

Social networks also influence the formation of new communication styles, such as "chat" or "SMS" styles. These styles are characterized by the use of emojis, stickers, GIFs, and other visual elements that help convey emotions and mood without using words. As a result, the text becomes more visualized and emotionally rich, which, on one hand, allows for a more precise conveyance of the interlocutor's mood and feelings, but on the other hand, reduces the need for complex linguistic constructions and descriptive expressions. Thus, the language of social networks becomes simpler but is enriched with visual elements, creating a new kind of written culture. The positive influence of social networks on the development of the Russian language lies in their contribution to its democratization and openness. In social networks, anyone can become an author, express their thoughts, and share them with a wide audience. This leads to an increase in the diversity of language forms and styles, as different user groups (e.g., bloggers, influencers, representatives of various subcultures) bring their unique features to the language. Social networks allow for the preservation and popularization of dialects and local speech characteristics, highlighting regional identity. Moreover, the internet becomes a platform for linguistic creativity, where new words, expressions, and memes are created, which may eventually enter the official lexicon.

On the other hand, social networks also have a negative influence associated with language simplification and a decrease in its standardization. Incorrect usage of words, ignoring grammatical norms, and the increase in borrowed words — all these factors may contribute to the loss of language culture and a decline in literacy levels among users. This is especially relevant for young people who actively communicate on social networks and often adopt simplified forms and incorrect constructions.

In conclusion, social networks play an important role in the development of the modern Russian language, exerting both positive and negative influences on its evolution. On one hand, they contribute to the expansion of linguistic possibilities, the emergence of new words and forms, making the language more flexible and adapted to the dynamic conditions of communication. On the other hand, they may lead to simplification and a decline in language quality if users do

not adhere to norms and standards. It is important to be aware of and account for this influence to preserve the uniqueness and richness of the Russian language in the context of the modern digital era.

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